

GLOBAL PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATION THEORY

¹Feruza Boymurodova Ziyot qizi, ²Xolmirzayeva Sevinch Sherzod qizi

¹MA Internatinal Education English Teacher,Uzbekistan State World Languages University

²1st year student at Uzbekistan State World Languages University Translation theory faculty

Abstract. *This article explores the intricate challenges that have encountered in the realm of translation on an international level. It emphasizes the importance of translation in facilitating dialogue amidst varied linguistic and cultural contexts and lays the groundwork for addressing prevalent concerns within the field.*

Keywords: *Translation, global problems, quality assurance, cultural nuances, inclusivity. Linguistic understanding, accessibility, cultural sensitivity.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье исследуются сложные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются в сфере перевода на международном уровне. Он подчеркивает важность перевода для облегчения диалога в различных языковых и культурных контекстах и закладывает основу для решения распространенных проблем в этой области.*

Ключевые слова: *Перевод, глобальные проблемы, гарантия качества, культурные нюансы, инклюзивность, Лингвистическое понимание, доступность, культурная чувствительность.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola xalqaro miqyosda tarjimashunoslik sohasida duch kelinayotgan muammolarni o'rganadi. Shu bilan birgalikda turli lingvistik va madaniy kontekstlarda muloqotni osonlashtirishda tarjimaning muhimligini va bu sohada keng tarqalgan muammolarni hal qilish uchun asos yaratadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tarjimashunoslik, global muammolar, sifat kafolati, madaniy nuanslar, inklyuziv, Lingvistik tushuncha, foydalanish imkoniyati, madaniy sezuvchanlik.*

In a world where globalization is becoming more crucial and communication knows no bounds day by day, the importance of translation is vital. It is impossible to conceptualize our current era where language barriers exist that understanding and empathy go beyond linguistic differences. Translation studies in a globalized sphere is considered as a bridge which connects diverse cultures, smoothes meaningful dialogue, and fosters mutual understanding.

As the complex sides of globalization are emerging, translation studies serve as the most effective interaction among various languages as well as cultures. Even though technology is accepted by many as the most innovative, easy method to translate, from diplomacy to business, literature to media, the impact of translation extends far and wide, shaping our perception of the world.

A translation is a text derived from another text in another language, exhibiting qualities of equivalence to that source text, such that the derived text can be taken as a substitute for the original text [1]. Translation cannot exist without theory. Theory is essential in translation because it sets the rules and meanings that guide every translation. It serves as the foundation upon which translations are evaluated. It's crucial to use the right theory to determine whether a translation is appropriate. If the translation process doesn't follow translation theory, the resulting translation will likely be unsuccessful and won't achieve its intended purpose. Additionally, translation theory is based on a mixed field such as language, culture, philosophy. This combination aids is to understand how the translation process goes as well as how people from various countries communicate. But the world that is constantly changing and technology advancing, this section

witnesses a myriad of problems that may affect everyone, no matter where they are. In this article, we are trying to provide some global challenges that have more impact on translation compared to others (Picture1).

Global problems in translation theory	Concerns
Machine translation and Technology	Accuracy/quality, loss of human touch, privacy and security concerns
Ethical consideration	Accuracy/Fidelity, cultural sensitivity/appropriateness
Linguistic and cultural nuances	Idiomatic expressions/Figurative language, Cultural references and context-specific meanings
Accessibility and inclusivity	Language disparities, digital divide, cost barriers

❖ **Machine translation and technology.** It has affected this field with its both new opportunities and challenges. This way of translation is based on automated algorithms that may result in the loss of human touch (also diminishing the empathy, creativity and cultural sensitivity, the main ingredients of the content). A lot of translators are facing problems when they are dealing with complex linguistic structures as well as context-dependent meanings. Because cultural as well as linguistic views are different in every nation, translations that are nonsensical, inaccurate, undermining the quality and most importantly the reliability of translated content.

❖ **Ethical considerations.** Another essential point, covering various worries that influence how translators behave and make choices. The person has a responsibility to convey the meaning as well as intent accurately in the new languages. They have to keep similar words, ideas while showing the presented feelings, background of the original text. The common dilemma faced by translators is working with politically sensitive or controversial content.

❖ **Linguistic and cultural nuances.** Every language contains idiomatic expressions or figurative language which do not have direct equivalents in other new languages. Mostly, misinterpretation or mistranslation of idioms may lead to confusion or distortion of the original text. For example: “It’s raining cats and dogs”, original text in english and literal translation in another language will be: “Esta lloviendo gatos y perros”. The literal meaning is not conveying the intended thing in the original text.

❖ **Accessibility and inclusivity.** Accessing translation help is not the same everywhere. There are some languages which do not have enough help with translation. This makes it hard for people who speak minority languages or indigenous languages to communicate, learn. As an example; remote villagers of the Amazon rainforest struggle to comprehend the content due to the lack of translation resources when they encounter government documents, educational materials.

In conclusion, problems in translation are not as less as we expected. And we should not forget that it affects how we communicate with each other, how we get information. Whether it is not having enough translators for certain languages or dealing with tricky situations, there is a lot to figure out. Also, by training translators better, being more aware of different cultures, using the technologies, it is possible to move forward.

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